

GUIDELINES FOR STANDARDIZATION & DEVELOPMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SCALE / TESTS

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Introduction :- Research in the discipline of education has increased enormously in the last decade. It has also taken new direction & identified new areas for investigation & exploration. Psychological testing in India has now crossed the experimental stage. Although many American or British tests and Inventories will continue to be adapted in future. New & original tests and Inventories has already been constructed in Indian language. Time has now been ripe for developing new techniques of construction & standardization of Tests in India.

For example If we describing achievement test, we shall particularly refer to standardized tests that are commercially available. These tests differ from teacher made objectives type tests in many ways.

Concept & Meaning of Standardized tests :- The word standardization explain the basic difference between what we call standardized & informal objective type tests. Standardization means the process of finding comparative norms. When we standardize a test, we analyse the curriculum very critically select items carefully & observe more strict standards than the informal objective type tests norms have to be given in any standardized test.

Standardization literally means 'brought to a level or standard'.

Many researchers stated various definitions of standardized tests.

C.V. Good :- The standardized test is a test for which content has been selected and checked empirically, for which norms have been established, for which uniform methods of administering and scoring have been developed & which may be scored with a relatively high degree of objectivity.

Lee J. Cronbach :- A standardized test is one in which the procedure, apparatus & scoring have fixed so that precisely the same test can be given at different time & places.

Standardization is however, more commonly done in achievement, intelligence and aptitude tests than in personality tests.

Important Points of Standardized tests :-

- 1) Standardized tests are based on uniform curriculum in many schools in a province or the whole nation.

- 2) Standardized tests are concerned with the whole field of knowledge or ability tested.
- 3) In standardized tests norms are given for various groups of person on age, grades, reality, urbanity, sex or other basis.
- 4) In standardized tests use of sources such as opinion of judges, articles, general books, previously standardized tests, etc. is made
- 5) The content is standardized i.e. item selection has been done vigorously, after careful scrutiny and by competent judges.
- 6) Scoring has been standardized i.e. scoring keys are prepared, definite rules for scoring have been formulated etc.
- 7) Administration is standardized i.e. directions time-limit, etc. are worked out carefully.
- 8) Statistical analysis is also done more vigorously.
- 9) Interpretation has been standardized, i.e. norms for various groups are provided.

Specific Guidelines in Scale development :-

Through eight steps any investigator will be developed a standardized test.

8 steps :-

- 1) Determine clearly what it is you want to measure.
- 2) Generate in item pool.
- 3) Determine the format for measurement.
- 4) Have initial item pool reviewed by experts.
- 5) Consider inclusion of validation items.
- 6) Administer items to a development sample.
- 7) Evaluate the items.
- 8) Optimize scale length.

Importance of standardized tests :- Standardization has come to stay in psychology & education. Standardized of procedure is very essential in experiments, research, test-constructions & even survey. In experiments, the use of standardized procedures in testing of content is essential. Standardized tests are useful in comparing achievement of individual or groups. Also it is comparing achievement in various fields of knowledge or performance, with the help of these standardized tests performance of various grades and institutions will be compared. For quality sustenance & Enhancement in Teacher Education.

References --

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